

First year engineering students' internal and perceived expectations

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ABSTRACT

First-year students' expectations when entering the university play a central role in how they experience higher education. While there has been a significant number of studies on first-year students' experiences, much less is known about which role expectations play on a qualitative level. In this study, we will approach the question; How students' expectations of higher education shape and are shaped by their experiences of entering the university. By drawing on a qualitative thematic analysis of nine interviews with first-year students in an electrical engineering program, we found that students' expectations to themselves and perceived expectations from others, are key elements in experiencing the learning environment and culture at the university. Grounded in the empirical material and in light of the contemporary research literature on first-year students, learning environments and university

pedagogy, we explore students' positions and aim to better understand the social mesh that they interact within during their first year at the university.

1 INTRODUCTION

Entering higher education is a major step for students and describes a significant transition in their personal and professional development. The transition into higher education is often accompanied with uncertainties and expectations. Students need to find their spaces and negotiate their role and social relations to other students and educators. On a disciplinary level, enculturation of students into engineering practices plays a central role [1]. In other words, students need to learn and assimilate knowledge, practices, and values of both disciplinary engineering cultures and social cultures surrounding their study program and the university in more general terms.

Furthermore, expectations first year students bring with them, either explicit or implicit, play a central role in how they experience higher education [2]. While there has been a significant number of studies on first-year student experiences, much less is known about which role expectations play on a qualitative level [3].

With this in mind, this study will be centred around the question; *How do students' expectations of higher education shape and are shaped by their experiences of entering the university?* We will explore this question by drawing on a qualitative thematic analysis of nine interviews with first-year students from the electrical engineering study program at the Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU).

Grounded in the empirical material and in light of the contemporary research literature on first-year students, learning environments and university pedagogy, we argue that transitioning from high school to university can be challenging on many levels. By exploring students' positions, we want to better understand the social mesh that they interact within during their first year at the university.

In the discussion, we will draw upon social identity theory (SIT) and system justification theory (SJT) to provide a conceptual framework to understand students' experiences. SIT approaches identity processes as embedded in social meshes and describes how group behaviours are influenced by status differences, perceived legitimacy and overall in- and outgroups [4]. In addition, SJT provides entry points to how students justify the system and culture that they are part of [5]. We argue that a closer examination of how students' transition and adjust is of general interest for engineering education and that the findings from this study have both practical and research implications.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Research context

The context of this study is a five-year integrated master's program in electrical engineering at NTNU called Electronic Systems Design and Innovation. This is a

program that admits 120 students every year and is one of 17 five-year integrated engineering master's programs at NTNU. All of these are among the programs with the highest admission requirements in Norway, though with significant differences between the 17 programs.

Associated with the Electronic Systems Design and Innovation program is a student organization, Omega, that provides social and extra-curricular arenas for students. Omega is organized and run entirely by students on a voluntary basis and takes responsibility for welcoming new students to the study program through social events, parties, and inauguration rituals, being a social facilitator throughout the year, and creating connections between students and industry. With this in mind, many students experience Omega as a main social arena from day one at university. Omega is made up of various committees, which in total organizes almost all of Omega's activities.

The students can choose between different committees with different activities where for example some arrange social events, others brew beer, and some are a part of the board. The committees are tightly knit to the industry, both through sponsorships and arranging meetings between students and companies. In addition to Omega, there are various other technical student organizations, not connected to a specific program, that provide additional social arenas for students oftentimes centered around realizing a specific technical project, e.g. Formula Student.

2.2 Research design

To explore the question; How students' expectations of higher education shape and are shaped by their experiences of entering the university, we draw upon a qualitative case study approach [3] with semi-structured in-depth interviews. In total, twelve first year students were recruited and gave their informed consent to be interviewed. Eight individual interviews and one group interview with four students were conducted. The students were recruited amongst the entire student population and signed up voluntarily. The interviews lasted 45 minutes on average and covered group dynamics, sense of purpose and belonging, design thinking, diversity, culture, and interdisciplinarity. All interviews were conducted in Norwegian (the students' mother tongue), and later audio-recorded and transcribed. Only the sections used in the results were translated to English and students were given pseudonyms.

For the analysis, the interviews were pooled together and a thematic analysis approach [4] was used to identify, analyze, and describe patterns and themes within the data. The material was read and re-read to explore how students' expectations of higher education shape and are shaped by their experiences of entering the university. Through the iterative analysis process, we identified themes that emerged from the interviews. These themes were further explored by considering relevant literature and using it as an additional perspective to develop and deepen the thematic analysis. In this study, we will present three themes that emerged from the analysis: *finding themselves*, *discovering social arenas within their study program*, and *positioning their study programs in relation to others*.

3 RESULTS

Based on the qualitative, exploratory analysis, it is apparent that students' own expectations and perceived expectations from others, are key elements in how they experience their learning environment and the overall culture at the university. Their expectations influence how they view themselves and how they position themselves in relation to others in a complex social mesh of rituals, traditions, and hierarchies. The interviews also reveal a strong dynamic in how students negotiate their own positions and are enculturated into the university culture both disciplinary and social.

3.1 Finding themselves

Grounded in the empirical material, it is clear that the students hold strong expectations towards being at the university when transitioning from high school. Furthermore, these expectations are not necessarily fixed, explicit, or coherent and an apparent finding in the material is that students continuously contradict themselves throughout the interviews. While students commonly answered that they did not have any expectations, when talking about their experiences from entering higher education and being a student, they clearly build upon and draw from the expectations they hold themselves and those of others.

One area where this becomes obvious in the empirical material is relation to their choice to become engineers. Here, the answers varied from wanting to pursue a genuine interest, to utilizing grades, following in their parents' footsteps, and achieving status and power. Status and power were mostly indirectly expressed in comparison to other professions, where engineers were compared to professions which are usually associated with lower status and power. One student expressed the desire of status directly, but more as a confession than a statement.

And a little bit due to status, I have to admit. It is a little bit like, if you can study engineering, you should (S7)

Another aspect of students' expectations that came up is that it can be tough going from being the best in your class to just being average amongst others who were also used to being the best. Becoming an electrical engineering student at NTNU requires relative high grades to be admitted. It appears that several of the students are struggling more with finding their place and building their professional identity around being one amongst many rather than being the smartest in a group. As a result of this, it turns out that they start perceiving themselves as average compared to everyone else.

You are used to hearing that you are the best in your class. And known to others as the best. And then you come to a place where everyone has the same experience. Suddenly, you do not feel so smart anymore. You do not stand out anymore... it has to do with the fact that I was the smartest, and now I am not anymore. I am not used to struggling in school. It's not like I'm stupid, but it's hard. I planned to be a straight A student, but now I'm more like a "passed" student. Because now I've met people who are a lot smarter than me, I thought I was that person, but I'm not. (S1)

In addition, students are unsure about the social norms in the cultures around their study program. They try to find a balance between positioning themselves in a way where they are seen as neither the most nor the least intelligent.

Simultaneously, several of the students reflect on the positive aspects that come from not being “better” than everyone else. This includes using the other students as a resource, rather than competing against each other. The students point out that they do not see the point in competing against others who are on the same level as themselves.

I have been able to use the other students more like resources now. Something that I did not feel before, before I came to the university that is. (S3)

3.2 Discovering social arenas within their study program

Upon entering the university, students start to navigate the social and professional landscape and try to find their way. The results reveal that an important part of this is becoming a part of the student organization at their study program and joining a committee. These committees appear to have great influence on the students’ learning environments and overall culture. In all the conducted interviews, students have pointed out the significance of these committees. The statements made, suggest that the students perceive joining a committee as an expectation to be a part of the social life of a student.

There seems to be a plethora of information about joining a committee and what it means to join a committee. During the interviews, the students were asked about why they wanted to join and several students expressed that joining a committee was a way of getting access to important social arenas. Not being a part of a committee, can lead to the feeling of being left out.

There was a lot of advertisement about the committees all the time. So, I don’t find it strange that so many students wanted to join, when you are surrounded by this information all the time... it’s a pity though, because there aren’t enough places for everyone to join. So, everyone that wants to join, cannot. It is a pity because they will miss that social arena, especially since a lot of students want to join as well. (S8)

Another student reveals that joining a committee did not feel like a big deal at first, but in retrospect played a central role in the process of becoming a student. She explains that if you are not a part of a committee or the “right” committee, you are labelled as “outcasts”.

I wish I could change or influence the existing culture more. Or be more a part of it. I don’t know if it is just me that has not participated enough. I didn’t know that committees were such a big deal, like everyone portrayed them to be. I have applied for a committee, but I didn’t know if you do not join a committee, you are practically nothing... I am in the revue committee and thought to myself “okay, this is cool”. But no one views the revue as a legitimate committee. At the student organization ball, all the committees had their own table, but the revue group didn’t even have a table. And the students who weren’t in a committee at all, sat all the way in the back and were like “outcasts”. (S1)

Yet another student reflects on her first days at the university, where it seemed like everyone had joined student organization committees quickly and without much thought. Not just one committee, but multiple ones. She later realized that this did

not work for her and became a roadblock in her studies. She describes her impression when arriving at the Ada-day – a project to promote technological studies to recruit more women.

When I arrived during the Ada-day, I got the impression that everyone had a student organization committee, a technical committee and did some other fun things and had time for hobbies in the side. And that they still had time to do the things they wanted to during the week. I found out after just to committees, that this didn't work for me. Where one of them didn't even take much work. I noticed that it was just mentally draining to just be a part of it, more draining than actually just doing the work that was required of me. Now I feel much more relaxed knowing that I can focus on my studies, without worrying about all the other stuff I should be doing. (S2)

3.3 Positioning their study programs in relation to others

When describing both the decision for choosing their study program and how they are experiencing it, the students draw heavily on comparing and positioning their study program in relation to other study programs. When choosing a study program, the common approach seems to be to choose based on your grades and aiming to be admitted to the study program with the highest possible admission requirement.

There is an existing hierarchy within our society and university. It seems that people think that you should just swoop into your place (in the hierarchy). If you have a 6.2 GPA (grade scale= 1-6), then you are supposed to choose indøk (Industrial Economics and Technology Management, the engineering program in Norway with the highest admission requirements). If you choose something else, it will be like «what are you doing? You are not supposed to be here». Passing on the notion that if you do not max your GPA, it will be a waste. (S7)

Once at the university, several chose to portray their own situation by ranking their program compared to others, both technical and non-technical study programs. The students illustrate a hierarchy, where they have a specific place, not at the top, but not far from it. Even before being fully enculturated into the university culture, the students pick up on existing social norms that exist on how to talk, relate, and view other study program. There is a known “feud” between the technological and humanistic studies. One of the students shares a story from the beginning of the semester illustrating this.

It might be because you don't have so much contact with people from the other study programs. I remember a situation from the initiation weeks at the university. We were at a student's house at a place in Trondheim. A person peaked through the window and asked where we studied. And I remember one girl lying about what she was studying, she said that she went to our university, because she knew that we went to this specific campus (with the technological study programs). It turned out that she went to BI (a private business school). So, this shows that there is a culture at our campus (Gløshaugen), that we are better than other studies. (S5)

When asked about where the notion of technological studies being “better” than other studies came from, the student points out that he has been told from former/senior students how the culture at NTNU and the electrical engineering program is and has always been. He emphasizes that these assumptions are unfortunate.

It is mostly from people around you. Things I have heard from last year's students. It is unfortunate. There is no reason for walking around thinking that you are better than everyone else. I do not feel like I think like that. But you hear it from people. There have not been any bad vibes, it might be more as a joke. But then again, there is always some truth behind a joke. (S5)

Another student describes what she has encountered as a common attitude at the university. The description contains how the campus where the technology programs are at home is perceived as better than the campus for other study programs. Even within the technological studies, there is a known hierarchy. She points out that this feeling has grown stronger after being a part of the university culture for a while.

I feel like there is an attitude at Gløshaugen (campus at the university), to start with- Gløshaugen is above all other places. This is where the hardest, toughest, smartest people study. Like a God-complex. And within, you have the really hard study programs. If you are just enrolled in a bachelor's study program you are just an engineer, not a sivil engineer... the industrial economy study program for example, is not perceived as having a very high status within Gløshaugen, but this study program has very high status elsewhere. This is a feeling I have. I did not think that it would be as strong as after I came here. I got this feeling after I came here, a lot more than when I applied. (S7)

4 DISCUSSION

Building on the empirical material, we will in the following discuss how students' expectations of higher education shape and are shaped by their experiences of entering the university. On a general level, based on the findings in this study, it is clear that the students' expectations before entering the university do not always align with their experiences after being admitted, which is in line with earlier investigations into first-year experiences [1]. Furthermore, it is apparent that their expectations of the university have a clear connection to their experiences from high school, including what they expect from themselves and others professionally.

The process of entering the university is a turbulent experience for students, where they have to realign their views of themselves to match their lived experience, a process that is shaped by their expectations, i.e. students who did not expect the social importance of the committees and feel left out when having problems joining or students who expected joining a committee would be socially important, but where the activities left them mentally exhausted.

From the interviews, it is clear that this process is tightly linked to students finding their role in the social hierarchy at the university. In the following, we will discuss three dimensions of this positioning process within the social hierarchy at the university: students' individual relations to each other, the role of social committees, and between study programs. First, when transitioning into university, the students need to reassess their own expectation of how they view themselves, including their own capabilities and knowledge, in relation to others in the same program. One of the students described it as "swooping into your place in the hierarchy". Previously, it has been found that this perception of oneself in relation to other students can affect behavior when collaborating in project courses, giving more meaningful tasks to the students that are perceived as more knowledgeable [5]. Second, the students need

to position themselves in relation to other students in the same student organization, with a membership in a committee as both an indicator and a generator of social attractiveness, with strong existing assumptions that new students will want to join one. Third, the students need to understand what status their choice of study program gives them in relation to students outside their program. Lastly, the students reveal that the choice of applying to engineering somewhat motivated by status and the expectations of those around them, not necessarily meaning only their parents, but other people in their community as well.

According to social identity theory (SIT) [6], students will derive a positive self-concept from being a member of a group, thereby favoring their own in-group to create a higher self-esteem. Simultaneously, there is a clear hierarchy between groups, as illustrated in the empirical material where the revue-committee is described as an out-group amongst the committees. It is also apparent that students constantly compare their own study program and see it in relation to other study programs. Being enemies with other student organizations, is portrayed as a joke, and by doing this it is possible to create an in-group within the student organization. This recurring theme is apparently a known topic both within and outside the university.

The high status of the student organizations creates a situation where they seem to have monopoly on how and where student culture and learning environments are negotiated. Students perceive that they are required to spend a set amount of time on committee work, and most spend significant amounts of time on the social events connected to the committee. The more time they spend, the more influence the committee will hold over the members, in turn making the committee as an in-group even more important for the students' university experience.

Building on system justification theory (SJT) [7], we see the students justify the social hierarchy through ego justification, group justification, and system justification. Ego justification describes the process by which students feel better about themselves by viewing themselves as better than other students, both in their own program and other programs. Group justification captures how committees are perceived as valuable places to be and creating value for others, whereas differences between programs and campuses can be approaches on the level of system justification.

Furthermore, the empirical material gives the impression that attitudes, justifications and overall culture is being passed on from one generation to the next, even though the students reveal that there are many aspects of the culture they do not like. The strong rituals and norms within the student organization might hold on to predefined connotations and prejudices, which several of the students' descriptions illustrate.

In conclusion, the interviews reveal that the students have expectations to both themselves and to others when entering university, expectations that are quickly shaped by the process of finding one's place in the university's social hierarchy through maneuvering the strong established expectations already present in the programs, organizations, and committees, creating an experience predefined by the strong cultural norms of what it means to be a student.

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